

CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS: TACKLING FOOD WASTE FOR A SUSTAINABLE SARAJEVO

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Abstract

Circular economy is not a new term. It has been used since ancient times in various societies, and it meant the saving, utilization of current materials and the conversion of old into new usable products. Today, this term is used in all countries all over the world, and is widely known through the implementation of different projects and activities. Some countries actively implement circular economy programs to a large extent, while in less developed countries activities in this area are less represented. Thus, economic, environmental and sustainable challenges that countries face have both negative and positive aspects. The focus of this paper is to show how the City of Sarajevo implement sustainable food consumption projects, which mean a positive step, from reducing environmental pollution, not wasting food, to donating it to charity. Digital tools used in Sarajevo to reduce food waste will also be presented. Through the analysis of strategic plans and desk analysis, the study found that the impact of different projects in the City of Sarajevo can improve the environment, make better problem-solving solutions for all citizens in Sarajevo, which will be provided in the conclusion of this paper.

Keywords: circular economy, sustainability, wasting food, city of Sarajevo, food consumption

INTRODUCTION

The impact of circular economy is enormous, both on different sectors and on individuals now days. Although adequate procedures and regulations specifically addressing the circular economy do not yet exist, this concept is nevertheless widely

applied in many countries. Recently, it has gained notable importance, as has the term "circular economy" itself. However, let us take a step back in time and encourage reflection on the fact that many cultures historically practiced circular economy principles within their households. They repaired items instead of discarding them, conserved resources, and created innovations from old products. In this context, if we refer to it at all, the circular economy is not as new as commonly believed; rather, the term itself is recent.

Indeed, numerous initiatives have been launched in many countries, including Bosnia and Herzegovina, by government institutions, businesses, and individuals. The non-governmental sector also stands out with projects related to the circular economy, food waste reduction, and similar areas. Relevant sectors compete to better implement programs and to engage young people in starting businesses within this field. Particularly noteworthy is the City of Sarajevo, as a government institution, along with its projects and initiatives in the area of the circular economy. As one of the contemporary scientific approaches, this paper presents a case study of the City of Sarajevo and the Sector for Sustainable Development, which deals with the initiation, creation and implementation of projects at the local and international level in the field of circular economy. Moreover, the paper will present the case of the City of Sarajevo through the existence of documents that are base for development of other programs.

Qualitative research was applied, and will be presented through the facts that can be confirmed from different sources, conclusions that represent the activities of individuals derived from observation of a given situation and random engagement. The information presented through this article can be used as a basis for development of specific documents and rules regarding circular economy as an example for other public institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

The circular economy holds great significance for humanity. Its substantial potential lies in generating economic, social, environmental, and other values. The circular economy aims to achieve zero waste and is based on the principles of taking, reducing, repairing, utilizing, recycling, and reusing. Many companies in Bosnia and Herzegovina have been implementing this concept for several years; some operate in local markets, while others serve international ones. However, there are no specific regulations or legislations dedicated to the circular economy, except for market regulations related to the export of products derived from circular economy practices.

Government institutions have adopted several documents and plans concerning the circular economy, but there remains significant potential for further development in this area in the future. Bosnia and Herzegovina faces many uncertainties, but as it moves closer toward the European Union, it must adopt numerous regulations and action plans on the circular economy, as this model represents a method of sustainable development worldwide.

This model can be realized starting from the planning phase itself, including raw material collection, as illustrated in the following picture.

Figure 1*The circular economy model*

Source:

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/resources/library/images/20230927PHT05951/20230927PHT05951_original.png

The picture illustrates how the circular economy contributes to the creation of a sustainable model through the reduction of raw materials, waste, greenhouse gas emissions, and similar factors. The European Union emphasizes that less waste results in more value across all aspects of life. By improving waste policies to support waste prevention and circularity, we can establish a well-developed sustainability framework. This model was adopted by the European Union as an action plan in 2020. Therefore, Bosnia and Herzegovina, as well as the countries of the Western Balkans, should adopt action plans for waste management and circularity to enhance the development policies of their countries.

SYSTEMATICAL APPROACH

A systemic approach to the circular economy initially involves the creation of legal regulations, programs, and action plans at the level of state institutions. One of the key challenges for Bosnia and Herzegovina is the development of legislation and methodologies that regulate the circular economy. The basic version of the circular economy methods starts with the 3Rs and 7 pillars, as illustrated in the following image:

Figure 2
The 3R-7 pillars

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Circular-economy-according-to-the-scheme-proposed-by-Ademe-4_fig1_344043150

The picture illustrates that the circular economy represents much more than the 3R concept; it is connected to many pillars related to different areas such as waste management, business, green economy, and similar fields.

Due to the comprehensive nature of the circular economy, many authors accept the 7R model, as illustrated in the following image:

Figure 2
7Rs Circular Economy model

Source: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Shaili-Vadera/publication/352994413/figure/fig5/AS:1042436042272770@1625547528355/Rs-Circular-Economy-Model.png>

According to author Vadera, this concept is based on an integrated approach consisting of seven components: Replace, Redesign, Re-modify, Recover, Repurpose, Recycle, and Refuse.

The foundation of this 7R model is based on sustainable development and environmental conservation. Considering that research has confirmed the existence of a vast amount of plastic and other waste materials on Earth, this concept, or model, is applicable and recommended to be integrated into the product life cycle in order to reduce the harmful impact on the environment.

At the end, we can conclude that a systemic approach is employed in the circular economy to integrate the connected pillars into a cohesive whole, illustrating the

methods and principles of the circular economy based on established laws and practices, and linking the interrelated areas of action in natural and social processes.

FOOD WASTE IN THE CITY OF SARAJEVO

The City of Sarajevo and the City Service for Sustainable Development represent a positive example of adopting a plan in the field of circular economy and implementing projects at both local and international levels. In this regard, the City of Sarajevo has adopted a plan for the prevention and reduction of waste and food losses until 2026.

According to the research cited in the Plan, it is shown that approximately 500 tons of food waste end up in landfills daily in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Based on the research, it was concluded that more than 12% of the daily waste disposed of in the Canton of Sarajevo consists of food waste. On the other hand, more than 20% of the population in Bosnia and Herzegovina live at or below the absolute poverty line. Therefore, food waste deserves a high level of priority. In this regard, the City of Sarajevo's plan proposes solutions that help reduce food waste and suggests synergy with all stakeholders who can contribute to addressing this significant issue.

Furthermore, based on estimates, the following is highlighted for Sarajevo Canton: Estimate for the current situation (based on limited available data):

- Daily food waste generation in Sarajevo Canton is between 50 and 63 tons (equivalent to 18,250 - 22,995 tons per year)

Calculation:

- $438,443$ (population of Sarajevo Canton) \times 0.00089 tons per capita per day of waste in BiH = 390.21 tons \times 0.15 (average percentage of food waste in municipal waste in Sarajevo, various data sources) = 59 tons of food waste per day (equivalent to $21,535$ tons per year)

Target estimate for food waste reduction by 2030:

- 29.5 tons of food waste per day (equivalent to $10,768$ tons per year).

Based on available information, an even greater amount of food waste is generated by food production companies. Therefore, the City of Sarajevo has initiated a food donation project for individuals in need, as well as a project like the Sarajevo Food Lab – a space where solutions are developed to prevent food waste generation, rescue surplus food, and recycle existing food waste to create new value.

It is also necessary to underline that the City of Sarajevo's plan includes the establishment of a Food Bank through the design of mobile applications to connect and inform people about food donation and collection.

This is just one example of the projects that the City of Sarajevo is implementing, alongside many others, encouraging young people to engage in food waste and circular economy activities, as well as businesses and individuals by sponsoring projects in these fields. To achieve positive results, they have established measures and activities, including but not limited to:

- Redirecting surplus food generated across all sectors of the food supply chain to people in need;

- Promoting a food waste prevention plan among all actors within the food supply chain by educating them about the problem and measures, and motivating their participation;
- Mapping all food waste generators and flows to identify potential surplus food donors, as well as mapping potential recipient organizations and charities willing to accept and redistribute donated surplus food;
- Establishment of a Food Bank.

In this context, one of the successful projects implemented under these measures is called 'Tanjir Više' (One More Plate). Tanjir Više is a civic initiative founded in Sarajevo with the goal of delivering surplus food from large events (such as weddings, birthdays, iftars, celebrations) to families in need. The operation works by citizens reporting surplus food via the Tanjir Više Facebook page, while volunteers, coordinated through a Viber group, collect the donated food within 30 minutes and deliver it to families in need. Currently, over 100 families receive food through this initiative

However, despite these advantages, it is necessary to emphasize that with the implementation of many projects in Sarajevo and beyond, there are challenges that require the specific adoption of regulations and measures in order to overcome these challenges.

A DIGITAL PLATFORM ENHANCING COLLABORATION IN THE CITY OF SARAJEVO

The City of Sarajevo, through all aspects of its operations and organization, strives to improve its performance both among its employees and by enhancing collaboration with citizens. In this way, the digital platform Decidim was established.

The goal of this platform was to create an efficient digital tool for democratic and active citizen participation in decision-making regarding activities, projects, voting on various initiatives, ideas, and similar matters. In recent years, the City of Sarajevo has also used this platform for citizen voting on the best food waste initiatives.

Decidim is a tailored digital solution designed to address the specific challenges faced by the citizens of Sarajevo. By creating this platform, the City of Sarajevo has enabled improved conditions for service delivery through Decidim—allowing the use of citizen feedback and the co-creation of important projects, ensuring that public services are designed to better meet user needs. This leads to enhanced service delivery, greater responsiveness, and higher satisfaction with the services provided by the City of Sarajevo.

Another benefit of Decidim is that it facilitates increased citizen participation. Decidim's citizen-centered approach has encouraged greater and more active involvement of citizens in decision-making processes in Sarajevo. By fostering better social cohesion, transparency, and equity, this digital platform has ultimately enabled a more responsible, fair, and improved relationship between citizens and the public administration of the City of Sarajevo.

This is a positive example that contributes to strengthening participatory democracy by enabling effective citizen participation in monitoring and decision-making on topics and projects that are important both to them and to the circular economy in general.

Figure 3
DECIDIM

Source: <https://decidim.sarajevo.ba/>

CONCLUSION

The impact of the circular economy is evident in every country, including the City of Sarajevo. Examples of good practice in this city can serve as a model for other Balkan countries to improve the implementation of circular economy projects. Moreover, necessary measures to be implemented in every public institution include the development of legal documents in the field of circular economy and specific related areas, starting with environmental protection, food waste reduction, and similar domains.

The City of Sarajevo has demonstrated through positive examples that its activities have substantial significance for citizens at the local level and beyond. The projects they implement contribute to environmental sustainability and address considerations of food waste residues. Within the Decidim online platform, ideas can be conceptualized, innovations promoted, and participatory democracy included. What is necessary is better collaboration among all government institutions in the City of Sarajevo regarding the advancement of circular economy measures and food waste management. It is anticipated that by 2030, this collaboration will be strengthened in line with the planned timeline to align with the principles of the circular economy and comply with EU standards.

REFERENCES

1. A.M. Järvenpää, J. Jussila, L. Kunttu, and I. Kunttu, Organizational Learning Practices to Develop Digitalization Capabilities in Circular Economy SMEs, <https://doi.org/10.55845/ULPA5543>, 2025.
2. B.S. Eiroa, The Social Importance of Researching Action-Oriented Circular Futures, <https://doi.org/10.55845/OYKZ1486>, 2025.
3. C. Cialani and S. Ugiati, A review on circular economy: the expected transition to a balanced interplay of environmental and economic systems, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959652615012287>, 2016.
4. Center for Policies and Management, White paper - Circular Economy in Bosnia and Herzegovina, https://zelenaekonomija.komorabih.ba/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Bijeli_Papir_Publikacija_28042022.pdf, 2022.
5. Cero, M., Silajdzic, I., Kurtagić M., Food waste in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2018.
6. CENER, Food waste reduction in Bosnia and Herzegovina, <https://cener21.ba/2018/09/15/reducing-food-waste-in-bosnia-and-herzegovina/>, 2018.
7. City of Sarajevo, Plan for the Prevention and Reduction of Food Waste and Food Loss 2023-2026, https://smart.sarajevo.ba/images/SFL/Food_Waste_Sarajevo_-_Plan_za_preveniraju_i_smanjenje_otpada_od_hrane_i_gubitaka_hrane_2021-2025_godina.pdf.
8. EU Library, <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20151201STO05603/circular-economy-definition-importance-and-benefits>, 2023.
9. Feleki, E., Tschapke, V., Borngeser, W., Kiesel, L., Transforming Urban Landscapes: Circular Economy Practices in European Cities, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43615-025-00674-5>, 2025.
10. Group of Authors, Conceptualizing the Circular Economy: An Analysis of 221 Definitions, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921344923001374>, 2023.
11. M:H, M.M., The circular economy, an element of a policy of ecological reconstruction - The point of view of working conditions and occupational risks. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344043150_The_circular_economy_an_element_of_a_policy_of_ecological_reconstruction_-_The_point_of_view_of_working_conditions_and_occupational_risks#pf4, 2020.
12. Mishra, S., Sahoo, D., Mohapatra, S., Barriers to Circular Economy Adoption in MSMEs: a WINGS Analysis of Challenges in Developing Economies, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43615-025-00668-3>, 2025.
13. S. Geisendorf, F. Pietrulla, The circular economy and circular economic concepts—a literature analysis and redefinition, *Thunderbird Int. Bus. Rev.*, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/tie.21924>, 2017.

14. Shieh, J.Lin.B, Chen, J., A circular economy model of sustainable growth, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43615-025-00559-7>, 2025.
15. S. Vadera, A Critical Analysis of Rising Global Demand of Plastics and Its Adverse Impact on Environmental Sustainability, *Journal of Environmental Pollution and Management*, 2021.
16. T.J. Foxon, A systemic approach to transitions towards circular economy: The case of Brighton and Hove, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666789421000301>, 2021.
17. UN, SDG goals, <https://sdgs.un.org/goals.2015>.